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Attitude, Self-Efficacy and Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics

NERYL JOY D. ALPACION

ORCID No. 0000-0003-3690-5613

Cor Jesu College

Digos City, Philippines

CRISTIAN T. CAMAÑAN

ORCID No. 0000-0002-8548-626X

camananchristian@gmail.com

Cor Jesu College

Digos City, Philippines

ARLYN JANE L. GREGORIO

ORCID No. 0000-0003-2690-6225

gregorioarlyn@gmail.com

Cor Jesu College

Digos City, Philippines

JUN MARK R. PANLAAN

ORCID No. 0000-0002-7787-1782

panlaanjunmark@gmail.com

Cor Jesu College

Digos City, Philippines

RANDY A. TUDY

ORCID No. 0000-0001-6535-6129

randytudy@cjce.edu.ph

Cor Jesu College

Digos City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics is an interesting but a very challenging subject. Several studies reported different factors which lead to students' poor performance in this subject. This study aimed to determine the influence of attitude and self-efficacy towards academic performance in Mathematics for Grade 8 students. It employed causal-correlational research design. The findings revealed that the level of academic performance of the students was satisfactory. In terms of the level of attitude towards Mathematics subject, it is either positive or negative. As to the students' self-efficacy, it is neither high nor low. No significant difference was found on the level of attitude and self-efficacy when grouped according to gender. It was also discovered that only attitude towards Mathematics manifested significant influence to academic performance. Students who have shown positive attitude towards the subject tend to perform well. Hence, performance in Mathematics can be improved by developing a positive attitude towards the subject. Parents, teachers and other stakeholders have the responsibility of helping the students in this aspect.

KEYWORDS

Mathematics, self-efficacy, attitudes towards Mathematics, correlation study, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The advent of technology in this information driven society poses a bigger challenge to learn the competencies in Mathematics subject. Throughout the world, more mathematics lessons are likely to be taught in schools and colleges than any other subjects. It has been considered as one of the most essential core in school curriculum. (Orton & Frobisher, 2004). However, performance in Mathematics continues to be a problem for many countries. For example in TIMSS 2011 report, achievement in Mathematics for sixth-grade students fell at or below Low International benchmarks (Mullis et al., 2011).

Low performance in Mathematics is also a problem in the Philippines. For instance, in the National Achievement Test (NAT) result for SY 2011-2012, students showed poorly in this subject with an overall Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 46.37. It is second to the lowest rank which is Science with 40.53. This is further confirmed with the poor showing of the country in the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS). Ironically, its neighboring countries like Singapore, South Korea, Hongkong, Chinese Taipei, and Japan are among the world's leader in Mathematics achievement (Mullis et al., 2011).

There had been studies which investigated the factors which lead to the low performance of students in Mathematics (Papanastasiou, 2002; Kidd et al., 2014; Barnes et al., 2014; Shafer, 2014; Grobler, 2014; Gerhard & Burn, 2014; Ma, 1999). One glaring problem is the curriculum. In his article entitled "A necessary renewal of Mathematics Education", Martin (2013) pointed out the strategy in teaching Mathematics which seems to prepare students as future Mathematicians although very few of these students will reach university level. In a case study in Kenya, it was discovered that understaffing, inadequate teaching/ learning materials, lack of motivation and poor attitudes by teachers and students, retrogressive practices are contributory factors to low performance of students in Mathematics (Mbugua et al., 2012)

In order to improve students' attitudes towards Mathematics, different strategies are being employed by teachers. For example, the use of technology-aided instruction improved students' attitudes towards the subject (Choi et al., 2013). Even social networking sites are used to help improve students' performance. For instance in the study of Gregory, Gregory & Eddy (2014), it was found out that those who participated in Facebook group discussion are more engaged in Mathematics subject. Using drawing activity was also found

out to have a positive effect on the performance of students in Mathematics (Arhin & Osei, 2013). The use of guided hyper learning method was also seen effective (Fathurrohman et al., 2013). Walkington, Petrosino & Sherman (2013) also discovered that context personalization has a positive effect to improving academic performance in Mathematics.

Despite applying different strategies and techniques, still the problem of low performance emerges. One of the reasons why students performed poorly in Mathematics is their attitude towards the subject. Several studies proved that their attitude had strong relationship with their academic performance (Parker et al., 2013).

Students' attitudes towards Mathematics should be given attention in teaching the subject if one is serious in advancing the performance of the students. This can only be developed in the presence of a healthy environment (Tran, 2012). Aside from environment, teachers' attitudes and beliefs, teaching styles and parental attitudes were identified as explanation factors that account for the student's attitudes towards mathematics (Asante, 2012; Vukovic et al., 2013). Hence, there should be a positive learning environment so that students can develop a positive attitude towards the subject which would lead to better performance (Tran, 2012). Having the opposite is fatal. For example, negative feedback from teachers was found out to be the strongest predictor of students Mathematics self-efficacy (Thomas, 2013). If students are anxious about the subject, they will likely be affected. This is supported by Ma (1999) who saw the significant relationship between anxiety towards mathematics and achievement in mathematics.

On the other hand, self-efficacy in Mathematics was also seen as strong factor. Several studies revealed the strong relationship between self-efficacy and Mathematics performance (Pampaka et al., 2011; Fast et al., 2010; Liang, 2010). Mathematics self-efficacy is developed most especially if there is positive teacher support and personal relevance (Aldridge et al., 2013). Students tend to eventually like the subject if they also like the teacher. Maximizing on the impact of self-efficacy, Cheema (2013) concluded that basic and simple measurements of math self-efficacy are likened to the effectiveness such as the mathematically elegant and complex counterparts. Self-efficacy in Mathematics is strongly related to the students' attitudes towards the subject. The former also showed significant effect on the tertiary entrance ranks (Vukovic et al., 2013).

Considering the number of literature which suggests the strong relationship between attitude and self-efficacy towards performance of students in Mathematics,

this study explored on the same path by investigating on the experience of Grade 8 students in the Philippines, in particular at Padada National High School, Davao del Sur. This study was anchored on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, which views human beings as cognitive, self-regulatory, and self-reflective (Yiu & Cheung, 2011)). Self-efficacy is major component on this theory which is defined as "beliefs in one's capabilities to organize and execute the course of action required to produce given attainments (Bandura, 1977). This study was also founded on Discrepancy Theory which argues that a negative attitude is a result of repeated failures or interruptions of planned actions (Mandler, 1989). Based from these theories, this study investigated if attitude and self-efficacy have to some degree affect academic performance in Mathematics.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the influence of attitudes and self-efficacy to academic performance in Mathematics for the Grade 8 students of Padada National High School, Davao del Sur, and Philippines. Specifically, it sought to discover the levels of academic performance, attitudes, and self-efficacy in Mathematics. It also identified if there are differences on the attitudes, self-efficacy and academic performance when the respondents were grouped according to gender. Finally, this study investigated on the influence of attitude and self-efficacy towards the students' performance in Mathematics.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive-correlational research design. The participants were Grade 8 students of Padada National High School, Padada, Davao del Sur, Philippines. An adopted questionnaire by Nicolaidou and Philippou (2003) was utilized while the first quarter grade of the students in Mathematics was used to measure academic performance. Mean, percentages, t-test, ANOVA and Multiple Regression analysis were employed to analyze the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings revealed an overall average grade of 81.76% of the students in Mathematics subject. It is on the level of approaching proficiency based on the K to 12 Curriculum Guidelines. In terms of attitudes towards Mathematics,

findings showed a mean average of 3.42 which means neutral. As to self-efficacy towards Mathematics, the mean average was 3.13, meaning neutral. When the respondents are grouped according to gender, t-test result produced a t-value of -1.152 with a p-value of .252, which indicates that there is no significant difference on the level of attitudes towards Mathematics. In terms of self-efficacy, no significant difference was also found with a t-value of -.889 supported by a p-value of .376. The same result was found in terms of academic performance in Mathematics. It showed a t-value of -.541 with a p-value of .589.

To prove that attitude and self-efficacy are strong predictors towards performance of students in Mathematics, as expounded in different studies and literature, regression analysis was utilized. Table 1 showed an F-value of 27.027, supported by a p-value of 0.000 which means that the model is fit. However, it only revealed an R^2 of 0.305, meaning only 30.5% of the data can be explained by the model. Further, the findings showed that only attitude towards Mathematics manifested significant effect or contribution to students' academic performance in the subject. Attitude towards Mathematics revealed a beta coefficient of 4.304. Thus, in every unit increase in the students' attitude, it will increase by 4.3 in their grades.

Table 1. Estimated Regression Coefficients of the Influence of Self-efficacy and Attitudes towards Students' Performance in Mathematics

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1. (Constant)	66.242	2.461		26.918	.000
SE	.229	.889	.024	.258	.797
AT	4.304	.738	.538	5.829	.000

a. *Dependent Variable: Grades*

b. *F-value = 27.027*

c. $R^2 = 0.305$

The result of the study confirmed the earlier results of the country's performance in Mathematics particularly in the National Achievement Test (NAT) results and TIMSS. The academic performance of the students in Mathematics was only on the approaching proficiency level. At this level, a student must have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understanding. Also, he/she needs only little guidance from the teacher or peers and possesses the competency of

transferring understanding independently through authentic performance tasks (DepEd Order 73, s. 2012). Based on the result, there is still so much to be done in the area of Mathematics. For not approaching the proficiency level, coupled with data from the NAT and TIMSS results, this study validated the country's need to work for the betterment in this particular subject. Considering the country's short-term development plan of closing the gap of classroom gap and improving the quality of educational policies, a second look at how the Filipino students' performance, especially in Mathematics, must be prioritized (NEDA, 2011). This is not only a cause for alarm but a call for an immediate action. If this problem is not addressed, the Philippines will continue to dig deep into the bottom of low performing country.

On the other hand, the K to 12 Curriculum, which is expected to boost students' competencies in all subjects, is a welcome note for the Philippines. For instance under the implementing rules and regulations of the enhanced Basic Education Curriculum Act of 2013, the Department of Education is mandated to adhere to the standards and principles to level up the quality of education in the Philippines. One of these standards and principles is the spiral progression approach to ensure mastery of knowledge and skills after each level (Implementing Rules, RA 10533). This is precisely what will enable students to enhance their skills and understanding of the subject. Subjects like Mathematics demands mastery of the skills learned not just in one setting but repeatedly and progressively done.

The study also affirmed the importance of students' attitude towards the subject as a big factor. There are studies which suggest means on how to help students develop a positive attitude towards the subject (Etuk et al., 2013; Zakaria et al., 2010; Tezer & Karasel, 2010). However, this study did not explore on what factors influence their attitude. While there are different aspects to consider, the role of the teacher is of primary importance. If students do not like their teachers in Mathematics subject, they tend to develop a negative attitude towards the subject (Etuk et al., 2013). Hence, teachers should show inspiring character and at the same time perform with competence and efficiency to teach the subject. This is a must for each teacher whether it is part of the mission or simply a professional demand. In the absence of a healthy environment and teacher's character, one cannot expect students to have a positive view and experience towards the subject.

The finding also revealed no gender differences on students' attitude and self-efficacy. It contradicted to several studies which portrayed girls having negative

perception and who are reportedly lagging behind in terms of Mathematics performance compared to boys (Wasike & Joseph, 2013; Vermeer et al., 2000). However, some studies reported gender differences but this time females have more positive attitude towards the subject than males (Mahad et al., 2012; Tekerek et al., 2011). Nevertheless, the result of this study is a good feedback tool for the school's stakeholders to look at attitude and self-efficacy of the students especially that the latter only gave a rating of neutral. It means the students do not possess a high level of positive attitude and self-efficacy towards Mathematics. It is no wonder why their performance did not reach the proficiency level.

Moreover, the positive effect of attitude towards Mathematics performance affirmed the findings of previous studies. Thus, one can predict a high-level performance if the students possess a positive attitude towards Mathematics. This is the same as saying how important it is to focus first on developing a positive attitude because it is an engine to propel students to perform well.

CONCLUSION

Mathematics subject continues to pose a challenge for students. With the result showing the low performance of the students in Mathematics, there is a need to go back to the drawing board beginning with curriculum review, teaching strategies and understanding students' psychology towards the subject. In particular, teachers are challenged to infuse new and effective strategies like those that have been proven to provide positive results (Gregory, Gregory & Eddy, 2014; Arhin & Osei, 2013; Choi et al., 2013; Fathurrohman et al., 2013; Walkington et al., 2013; Taclay, 2013; Limjuco, 2012). Moreover, much attention must be given invested into developing a positive attitude towards the subject. Since in this study attitude was found to have a strong effect towards academic achievement, teachers should make sure students continue to develop a positive attitude themselves. In the absence of this, one cannot expect a change for the better. The main challenge lies on the teachers who should be aware of the attributes which influence students' attitudes towards Mathematics because they are influential and significant factors, they must ensure to be a good model for making the students appreciates and love the subject. However, this does not excuse other stakeholders because good education is a product of unified efforts of all who are involved in the formation of the students.

While attitude showed significant influence, the model only explains around 30%, meaning there are other factors not included in the model. It is, therefore, recommended exploring other variables to build a more powerful model. Though

self-efficacy did not show significant influence, it does not mean teachers and other stakeholders will not work on helping students develop this factor. It has to be taken into account since other literatures and studies confirm its strong effect. This study is limited only to one school in the Philippines though the results validated previous findings.

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